

Use of fluorescent optical fibre probe for recording parameters of brain metabolism in rat model

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out on groups of clinically healthy male Wistar rats. Animals received distilled drinking water ad libitum for 1 month, water containing succinic acid, water containing zinc sulphate and succinate zinc. Using the method of fluorescence spectroscopy, the parameters of brain metabolism *in vivo* in a model of laboratory rats was investigated. Based on data obtained by fluorescence spectroscopy, we have registered a change in the degree of cellular respiration in different structures of the cerebral cortex with the toxic effect of zinc compounds and succinic acid on the oxygen exchange process.

Keywords: zinc compounds, succinic acid, zinc sulphate, brain metabolism, fluorescence spectroscopy, blood microcirculation, optical measurements *in vivo*, neurodegenerative diseases

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1. INTRODUCTION

Changes in metabolism in the structures of the brain are noted in many neurodegenerative diseases, generally in old age. Neurodegenerative diseases are a group of slowly progressing pathological states of the nervous system. They are characterised by the death of nerve cells, which leads to the development of specific neurological symptoms. This can occur at different ages but is mainly observed in older people.

It is a well-known fact that disruption of metabolic processes in brain structures are observed long before clinical manifestations. That is why the development of evaluation methods for metabolic disturbances in the brain presents itself as a real problem in fundamental medicine. The free form of zinc (Zn^{2+}) in the brain is present in the synaptic vesicles on the terminals of the glutamatergic nerves and is synaptically released during the activity of the neurons. Zn^{2+} is also associated with metalloproteins and is intracellularly mobilised under oxidative stress. Zn^{2+} plays a dynamic role in the physiology and the pathophysiology of brain function.

According to literature^{1,2}, an increase in the concentration of zinc compounds can trigger a pathogenic molecular process leading to the development of neurodegenerative diseases of the central nervous system^{3,4}. Also, exceeding the concentration of zinc in the body can cause disturbances in immune functions and provoke a shortage of chemical compounds, including iron or copper. Excess of zinc compounds for a long period can lead to the emergence of degenerative processes in the pancreas, liver⁵ and organs of the gastrointestinal tract.

At the same time, antioxidant therapy with succinic acid⁴ is capable of providing a neuroprotective effect in the development of neurodegenerative diseases. Succinic acid is an endogenous intracellular metabolite of the Krebs cycle

that performs a catalytic function. This acid increases the rate of reactions and stimulates the formation of ATP. Moreover, there is an antihypoxic effect of succinic acid due to an increase in the concentration of GABA in the brain tissue. Succinic acid helps to regulate cellular metabolism in pathological conditions, accompanied by oxidative stress. Also, the effect on brain tissues of small doses of a zinc succinate compound during its long intake into the organism is of particular interest.

One of the promising directions for studying the parameters of brain metabolism *in vivo* in a model of laboratory rats, is the recording of the spectrum by fluorescence spectroscopy⁶⁻⁸. This method is based on the excitation of the endogenous and exogenous fluorophores of biological tissue and registration of their fluorescence⁹. The method of fluorescence spectroscopy also has a high sensitivity and makes it possible to estimate the intensity of metabolic processes¹⁰, the state of oxygen metabolism of tissues and the distribution of fluorescent nanoparticles within the body¹¹.

This study aims to obtain the results of changes in metabolic processes in the cerebral cortex of rats *in vivo* under conditions of introduction of zinc sulphate, succinic acid and succinate in the drinking water.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Experimental studies were performed on clinically healthy male Wistar rats at the age of 5 months¹² (n = 6 in the group). Rats were obtained from the FSBI SCBT FMBA of Russia ("Andreevka" branch). Before the transfer of the animals to the clean zone of the vivarium and the beginning of the experiment, the animals were kept in quarantine for 14 days. When placed in quarantine, the veterinarian conducted a primary assessment of the animals' condition. Immediately before the transfer to a clean zone and the formation of experimental groups, the veterinarian conducted a clinical examination of the animals. In the study, animals were selected with no signs of health related abnormalities, so that the average body weight did not differ statistically between the groups. Each animal was assigned an individual number. The basic rules of maintenance and care corresponded to the standards set out in the sanitary rules for the arrangement, equipment and maintenance of experimental biological clinics (Vivarii) and the position-guidance "Laboratory animals". All procedures for routine animal care were carried out by the SOP of the CJSC "Retinoids".

Animals received distilled drinking water ad libitum for 1 month (group 1), water containing succinic acid at a dose of 25 mg per litre (group 2), water containing zinc sulphate at a dose of 3 mg per litre (group 3) and zinc succinate in a dose of 100 mg per litre (group 4). The manifestation and severity of pathological features were evaluated according to the corresponding standard procedure.

For the detection of fluorescence signals, excitation at 365 nm and 450 nm was used, which corresponds to the excitation wavelengths of the NADH and FAD. The fluorescence spectroscopy system with fibre-optical probe "LAKK-M" (SPE "LAZMA" Ltd, Russia) was used for the *in vivo* measurements (fig.1 a). The system provides multiwavelength excitation, detects emission, and processes the fluorescence signal. Its light sources include fluorescence excitation in UV (wavelength = 365 nm, power = 1.5 mW), blue (wavelength = 450 nm, power = 3.5 mW) and green light (wavelength = 532 nm, power = 4.5 mW). The abovementioned fluorescence excitation powers are provided at the tip of fibre probe, which induces an excitation light flux in the tissue of no more than 0.16 W m⁻² for 365 nm and 0.37 W m⁻² for 450 nm. The spectrometer was a polychromator with a diffraction grating, and a CCD (TCD1304AP, Toshiba, Tokyo, Japan) was used as the detector.

Figure 1. Experimental equipment: scheme of the "LAKK-M" device (a) and the areas of cortex observation (b)

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